

Online Supplements to:
“The equivocal mean age of parents in a cohort”,
published in *The American Naturalist*

François Bienvenu^{1,2}

¹*Center for Interdisciplinary Research in Biology (CIRB), CNRS UMR 7241,
Collège de France, PSL Research University, Paris, France*

²*Laboratoire de Probabilités, Statistique et Modélisation (LPSM), CNRS UMR 8001,
Sorbonne Université, Paris, France*

March 19, 2019

S1 Basic facts about Poisson point processes

In this section we recall basic results about Poisson point processes, focusing on the properties on which our calculations rely. Thus no attempt is made to state the results in full generality, and we do not preoccupy ourselves with technical conditions such as measurability. For a detailed presentation of Poisson point processes, see e.g. [Kingman \(1992\)](#) or [Daley and Vere-Jones \(2003\)](#).

It is common in modelling to assume that an event *occurs at rate* $r(t)$ *at time* t . Loosely speaking, this means that the probability that the event happens between t and $t + dt$ is independent of its previous occurrences, and is approximately $r(t) dt$. The rigorous way to formalize this is to say that the events are distributed according to an (inhomogeneous) Poisson point process with intensity r . Such a process can be seen as a random set of points characterized by the following properties: writing $N(I)$ for the number of points that fall in a fixed set $I \subset \mathbb{R}$,

- (i) $N(I)$ is a Poisson random variable with mean $\int_I r(t) dt$.
- (ii) $N(I)$ and $N(J)$ are independent whenever I and J are disjoint.

Note that the following useful fact is an immediate consequence of (i):

$$\mathbb{P}(N(I) = 0) = \exp\left(-\int_I r(t) dt\right). \quad (\text{S1.1})$$

Property (ii), often known as the *independent scattering* property, essentially says that Poisson point processes have a “completely random” structure.

E-mail address: francois.bienvenu@normalesup.org

From now on, we consider a fixed set $I \subset \mathbb{R}$ such that $\int_I r(t) dt < +\infty$. We let P be a Poisson point process with intensity r on I and denote by $N = \text{Card}(P)$ its number of points. Let X be a random point of I with density $t \mapsto r(t) / \int_I r(t) dt$, i.e. whose distribution is characterized by

$$\forall A \subset I, \quad \mathbb{P}(X \in A) = \frac{\int_A r(t) dt}{\int_I r(t) dt}, \quad (\text{S1.2})$$

and note in passing that

$$\mathbb{E}(X) = \frac{\int_I t r(t) dt}{\int_I r(t) dt}. \quad (\text{S1.3})$$

Then, conditional on $N = n$, P consists of n independent copies of X – that is, for every function φ ,

$$\mathbb{E}(\varphi(P) \mid N = n) = \mathbb{E}(\varphi(\{X_i : i = 1, \dots, n\})), \quad (\text{S1.4})$$

where $X_i, i = 1, \dots, n$, are independent copies of X .

A consequence of this is that the expected value of the average of the points in P is $\mathbb{E}(X)$. Formally, if $N > 0$ then we can define a random variable \bar{X} by

$$\bar{X} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t \in P} t. \quad (\text{S1.5})$$

We then have

$$\mathbb{E}(\bar{X} \mid N > 0) = \mathbb{E}(X). \quad (\text{S1.6})$$

Indeed,

$$\mathbb{E}(\bar{X} \mid N > 0) = \frac{1}{\mathbb{P}(N > 0)} \sum_{n \geq 1} \mathbb{E}(\bar{X} \mid N = n) \mathbb{P}(N = n), \quad (\text{S1.7})$$

and, for every $n \geq 1$,

$$\mathbb{E}(\bar{X} \mid N = n) = \mathbb{E}\left(\frac{X_1 + \dots + X_n}{n}\right) = \mathbb{E}(X). \quad (\text{S1.8})$$

In fact, given a function f , the exact same reasoning can be applied to

$$\bar{W} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{t \in P} f(t) \quad (\text{S1.9})$$

to show that

$$\mathbb{E}(\bar{W} \mid N > 0) = \mathbb{E}(f(X)). \quad (\text{S1.10})$$

We close this short overview with a fundamental result known as Campbell’s formula. This formula states that, for every function f ,

$$\mathbb{E}\left(\sum_{t \in P} f(t)\right) = \int_I f(t) r(t) dt. \quad (\text{S1.11})$$

In contrast to (S1.6) and (S1.10), which are consequences of the independent scattering property, Campbell’s formula is not specific to Poisson point processes.

S2 Expression of τ for discrete age structures

In discrete time, individual i has an integer-valued lifespan T_i and, at each age $t = 1, \dots, T_i$, produces $M_t^{(i)}$ new individuals, where the variables $M_t^{(i)}$ are integer-valued and independent of everything else. Here we will also need to assume that each variable $M_t^{(i)}$ is a Poisson random variable with mean m_t .

In that setting, the average \bar{X}_i of the ages at which individual i produces offspring can be defined as

$$\bar{X}_i = \frac{1}{N_i} \sum_{t=1}^{T_i} t M_t^{(i)}, \quad (\text{S2.12})$$

this definition being valid only when $N_i = \sum_{t=1}^{T_i} M_t^{(i)} > 0$. Note that, in this expression, each age at which i produces offspring is weighted by the number of offspring produced. This is similar to what is done for μ_1 , where each offspring contributes to the average age of the parents. But another possibility would be to weight all ages equally, that is, use the variable

$$\bar{Y}_i = \frac{\sum_{t=1}^{T_i} t I_t^{(i)}}{\sum_{t=1}^{T_i} I_t^{(i)}}, \quad (\text{S2.13})$$

where $I_t^{(i)} = 1$ if $M_t^{(i)} > 0$ and 0 otherwise.

Since $\bar{X}_i = \bar{Y}_i$ when individuals cannot give birth to several offspring simultaneously (or, more generally, when the number of offspring produced is either 0 or some constant m), the two definitions were equivalent in the continuous-time setting. But now, \bar{X}_i and \bar{Y}_i are two different and legitimate candidates for the “average age at which i produces offspring”. However, \bar{Y}_i does not lend itself to analysis as easily as \bar{X}_i and to obtain formula (5) – which is arguably the natural discrete-time equivalent of formula (3) – it is \bar{X}_i that should be used. Therefore, we define τ to be $\mathbb{E}(\bar{X}_i \mid N_i > 0)$.

The reasoning that lead to (3) could be adapted to obtain an expression for τ . However, it is also possible to deduce this expression directly from our results in continuous time. Indeed, the calculations of Section C of the Appendix are valid for general lifespans, including discrete ones: when ν is discrete, we simply have for any function φ

$$\int_0^{+\infty} \varphi(t) d\nu(t) = \sum_{t \geq 1} \varphi(t) p_t, \quad (\text{S2.14})$$

where $p_t = \mathbb{P}(T_i = t)$.

Moreover, observe that if we let the age-specific fertility m be the piecewise constant function defined by

$$m(t) = \sum_{s \geq 1} m_s \mathbb{1}_{]s-1, s]}(t), \quad (\text{S2.15})$$

where $\mathbb{1}_{]s-1, s]}$ is the function that evaluates to 1 if $t \in]s - 1, s]$ and 0 otherwise, then the number of offspring produced by an individual between ages $(t - 1)$ and t is a Poisson variable with parameter m_t . Thus, the only difference with the discrete setting is that the ages at which these offspring are produced are uniformly distributed in $]t - 1, t]$ instead of all equal to t .

Now, if we take the age-specific fertility to be the function $m^{(\varepsilon)}$ defined by

$$m^{(\varepsilon)}(t) = \sum_{s \geq 1} \frac{m_s}{\varepsilon} \mathbf{1}_{]s-\varepsilon, s]}(t), \tag{S2.16}$$

then the number of offspring produced between ages $(t - 1)$ and t is still a Poisson variable with parameter m_t , but this time the ages at which these offspring are produced are uniformly distributed in $]t - \varepsilon, t]$. Taking ε to zero, the mean age at childbirth will therefore tend to that of the discrete-time model. We spare the reader the straightforward but somewhat technical argument by which this can be made rigorous. Noting that, for continuous functions g ,

$$\int_0^t g(s) m^{(\varepsilon)}(s) ds \xrightarrow{\varepsilon \rightarrow 0} \sum_{s=1}^t g(s) m_s, \tag{S2.17}$$

we obtain the following discrete-time equivalent of (3):

$$\mu_1 = \frac{1}{c} \sum_{t \geq 1} \frac{\sum_{s=1}^t s m_s}{\sum_{s=1}^t m_s} \left(1 - \prod_{s=1}^t e^{-m_s} \right) p_t, \tag{S2.18}$$

where $p_t = \mathbb{P}(T_i = t) = \ell_t - \ell_{t+1}$, and

$$c = \sum_{t \geq 1} \left(1 - \prod_{s=1}^t e^{-m_s} \right) p_t. \tag{S2.19}$$

S3 Proof of $\mathbb{E}(\tilde{T}) \rightarrow \mathbb{E}(T^2)/\mathbb{E}(T)$ as $m \rightarrow 0$

In this section we prove that, when the lifespan T of a fixed individual has a second moment – a condition that is always met in practice – and the age-specific fertility is constant and equal to m , then the expected lifespan of individuals that produce offspring during their lifetime converges to $\mathbb{E}(T^2)/\mathbb{E}(T)$ as $m \rightarrow 0$. As seen in the main text, it follows immediately that $\tau \rightarrow \mu_1$, both in the continuous setting where offspring production occurs at a constant rate m during the lifetime of individuals and in the discrete setting where individuals produce a $\text{Poisson}(m)$ number of offspring at each integer-valued age $t \geq 1$.

Proposition 1. *Let T denote the lifespan of a fixed individual, and let \tilde{T} have the distribution of T conditional on reproduction in the model where reproduction happens at constant rate (or in the model where individuals produce $\text{Poisson}(m)$ offspring at each integer age $t \geq 1$ at which they are alive), i.e.*

$$\mathbb{E}(\tilde{T}) = \frac{\mathbb{E}(T(1 - e^{-mT}))}{\mathbb{E}(1 - e^{-mT})}. \tag{S3.20}$$

Then, if $\mathbb{E}(T^2) < +\infty$,

$$\mathbb{E}(\tilde{T}) \rightarrow \frac{\mathbb{E}(T^2)}{\mathbb{E}(T)} \text{ as } m \rightarrow 0. \tag{S3.21}$$

Proof. The following proof is due to Stephen P. Ellner and is a welcome simplification of my original proof.

Let $g(m, t) = (1 - e^{-mt})/m$, so that

$$\mathbb{E}(\tilde{T}) = \frac{\mathbb{E}(Tg(m, T))}{\mathbb{E}(g(m, T))}. \tag{S3.22}$$

Since

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial m}g(m, t) = (1 + mt - e^{mt})\frac{e^{-mt}}{m^2} \tag{S3.23}$$

and that $1 + x \leq e^x$ for all x , we see that $g(m, t)$ increases to t as m decreases to 0. By the monotone convergence theorem, it follows that $\mathbb{E}(g(m, T)) \uparrow \mathbb{E}(T)$ and $\mathbb{E}(Tg(m, T)) \uparrow \mathbb{E}(T^2)$ as $m \downarrow 0$. This terminates the proof. \square

S4 Proof of $\tau \leq \mu_1$

In this section we prove that μ_1 , as defined by formulas (1) and (2), is always greater than or equal to τ , as defined by formulas (3) and (5). This will be a simple consequence of the following lemma.

Lemma 1. *Let X be a positive random variable, and let g and h be positive functions such that $x \mapsto g(x)/x$ is nondecreasing and $x \mapsto h(x)/x$ is nonincreasing. Then,*

$$\mathbb{E}\left(\frac{g(X)h(X)}{X}\right)\mathbb{E}(X) \leq \mathbb{E}(g(X))\mathbb{E}(h(X)) \tag{S4.24}$$

Proof. Let Y be a random variable with the same distribution as X and that is independent of X . We have to show

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{E}(g(X))\mathbb{E}(h(Y)) - \mathbb{E}\left(\frac{g(Y)h(Y)}{Y}\right)\mathbb{E}(X) \geq 0 \\ \iff & \mathbb{E}\left(Xh(Y)\left(\frac{g(X)}{X} - \frac{g(Y)}{Y}\right)\right) \geq 0 \\ \iff & \mathbb{E}\left(Xh(Y)\left(\frac{g(X)}{X} - \frac{g(Y)}{Y}\right)\mathbf{1}_{\{X>Y\}}\right) \\ & + \mathbb{E}\left(Xh(Y)\left(\frac{g(X)}{X} - \frac{g(Y)}{Y}\right)\mathbf{1}_{\{X<Y\}}\right) \geq 0 \end{aligned} \tag{S4.25}$$

Since $x \mapsto g(x)/x$ is nondecreasing,

$$\left(\frac{g(X)}{X} - \frac{g(Y)}{Y}\right)\mathbf{1}_{\{X<Y\}} \leq 0 \tag{S4.26}$$

and since $x \mapsto h(x)/x$ is nonincreasing,

$$0 \leq Xh(Y)\mathbf{1}_{\{X<Y\}} \leq Yh(X)\mathbf{1}_{\{X<Y\}}. \tag{S4.27}$$

As a result,

$$\begin{aligned} & \mathbb{E}\left(Xh(Y)\left(\frac{g(X)}{X} - \frac{g(Y)}{Y}\right)\mathbb{1}_{\{X<Y\}}\right) \\ \geq & \mathbb{E}\left(Yh(X)\left(\frac{g(X)}{X} - \frac{g(Y)}{Y}\right)\mathbb{1}_{\{X<Y\}}\right) \\ = & -\mathbb{E}\left(Xh(Y)\left(\frac{g(X)}{X} - \frac{g(Y)}{Y}\right)\mathbb{1}_{\{X>Y\}}\right) \end{aligned} \tag{S4.28}$$

Plugging this into (S4.25) finishes the proof. □

Proposition 2. *Let T denote the lifespan of a fixed individual. Define the random variables M and M^* by*

$$M = \int_0^T m(s) ds \quad \text{and} \quad M^* = \int_0^T s m(s) ds \tag{S4.29}$$

in the case where reproduction occurs at a constant rate, and by

$$M = \sum_{s=1}^T m_s \quad \text{and} \quad M^* = \sum_{s=1}^T s m_s \tag{S4.30}$$

in the case where it takes place at integer-valued ages $t \geq 1$, so that, in both cases

$$\mu_1 = \frac{\mathbb{E}(M^*)}{\mathbb{E}(M)} \quad \text{and} \quad \tau = \frac{\mathbb{E}\left(\frac{M^*}{M}(1 - e^{-M})\right)}{\mathbb{E}(1 - e^{-M})}. \tag{S4.31}$$

Then, $\tau \leq \mu_1$.

Proof. First, observe that M^* is actually a deterministic function of M . Indeed, let ψ (resp. ψ^*) denote the function such that $M = \psi(T)$ (resp. $M^* = \psi^*(T)$). Since ψ is nondecreasing, if we define θ by

$$\theta(x) = \inf\{t \geq 0 : \psi(t) \geq x\}, \tag{S4.32}$$

then we have $M^* = \psi^*(\theta(M))$. To see this, note that $\theta(M) \leq T$ by construction and that $\theta(M) < T$ implies $\int_{\theta(M)}^T m(s) ds = 0$ (resp. $\sum_{s=\theta(M)}^T m_s = 0$), which in turn implies $\int_{\theta(M)}^T s m(s) ds = 0$ (resp. $\sum_{s=\theta(M)}^T s m_s = 0$). Thus, writing

$$g(x) = \psi^*(\theta(x)) \quad \text{and} \quad h(x) = 1 - e^{-x}, \tag{S4.33}$$

we have to prove

$$\mathbb{E}(g(M)) \mathbb{E}(h(M)) \geq \mathbb{E}\left(\frac{g(M)h(M)}{M}\right) \mathbb{E}(M). \tag{S4.34}$$

Clearly, M is a positive random variable, and the functions g and h are positive. Therefore, all we have to do to finish the proof is to show that $x \mapsto h(x)/x$ is nonincreasing and that $x \mapsto g(x)/x$ is nondecreasing, so that we can apply Lemma 1. First,

$$\frac{d}{dx} \left(\frac{h(x)}{x} \right) = \frac{e^{-x}(1+x) - 1}{x^2} \leq 0, \tag{S4.35}$$

since $1 + x \leq e^x$. Second,

$$\frac{g(x)}{x} = \frac{\psi^*(\theta(x))}{\psi(\theta(x))} = F(\theta(x)) \tag{S4.36}$$

where $F: t \mapsto \psi^*(t)/\psi(t)$. The function θ is nondecreasing by construction. The fact that F is nondecreasing can be shown by straightforward calculations, e.g., in the continuous case,

$$\frac{d}{dt}F(t) = \frac{m(t)\left(\int_0^t(t-s)m(s) ds\right)}{\left(\int_0^t m(s) ds\right)^2} \geq 0. \tag{S4.37}$$

However, it is more satisfying to see that $F(t)$ can be interpreted as the expectation of a random variable X_t with density $f_t(s) = m(s)\mathbb{1}_{[0,t]}(s)/\psi(t)$ in the continuous case, and with probability mass function $p_s^{(t)} = m_s/\psi(t)$ for $s = 1, \dots, t$ in the discrete case. It then is easy to see that X_t is stochastically dominated by $X_{t'}$ for $t < t'$, and so it follows immediately that $F(t) = \mathbb{E}(X_t) \leq \mathbb{E}(X_{t'}) = F(t')$. \square

S5 Example of calculation of τ

In this section we detail the calculations of τ in the case where the lifespan T of a fixed individual is a geometric variable such that for all $t \geq 0$, $\mathbb{P}(T_i = t) = (1-p)p^t$, and the age-specific fertility is constant and equal to m for all ages $t \geq 1$.

First, since

$$\frac{\sum_{s=1}^t s m}{\sum_{s=1}^t m} = \frac{t+1}{2} \tag{S5.38}$$

we see that, writing \tilde{T} for the lifespan conditional on reproduction,

$$\tau = \frac{1}{2} \left(\mathbb{E}(\tilde{T}) + 1 \right), \tag{S5.39}$$

where

$$\mathbb{E}(\tilde{T}) = \frac{\mathbb{E}(T(1 - e^{-mT}))}{\mathbb{E}(1 - e^{-mT})}. \tag{S5.40}$$

Now,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}(1 - e^{-mT}) &= 1 - \sum_{t \geq 0} e^{-mt} (1-p) p^t \\ &= 1 - \frac{1-p}{1 - p e^{-m}} \\ &= \frac{p(1 - e^{-m})}{(1 - p e^{-m})}. \end{aligned} \tag{S5.41}$$

Similarly,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbb{E}(T(1 - e^{-mT})) &= \sum_{t \geq 0} t(1-p) p^t - \sum_{t \geq 0} t e^{-mt} (1-p) p^t \\ &= \frac{p}{1-p} - \frac{(1-p) p e^{-m}}{(1 - p e^{-m})^2} \\ &= \frac{p(1 - e^{-m})(1 - p^2 e^{-m})}{(1-p)(1 - p e^{-m})^2}. \end{aligned} \tag{S5.42}$$

As a result,

$$\mathbb{E}(\tilde{T}) = \frac{1 - p^2 e^{-m}}{(1 - p)(1 - p e^{-m})} \quad (\text{S5.43})$$

and finally,

$$\tau = \frac{1}{2} \left(\frac{1}{1 - p} + \frac{1}{1 - p e^{-m}} \right). \quad (\text{S5.44})$$

S6 Computing μ_1 and τ for Compadre/Comadre

In this section, we detail how the data behind Figure 2 and Table 1 in the main text were obtained. The code and the data are provided as an Online Enhancement to the manuscript.

The [COMPADRE Plant Matrix Database](#) and [COMADRE Animal Matrix Database](#) each contain thousands of projection matrices for hundreds of species. However, not all of these matrices are suitable to compute μ_1 and τ . Indeed, for this we need:

- (i) The $\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{S} + \mathbf{F}$ decomposition of the projection matrix into its survival and fertility components.
- (ii) Non-zero \mathbf{S} and \mathbf{F} matrices.
- (iii) A survival matrix \mathbf{S} whose columns all sum to less than one, so that it can be interpreted as a substochastic matrix and that $(\mathbf{I} - \mathbf{S})^{-1}$ is always guaranteed to exist.

This leaves us with 3319 models in COMPADRE and 1245 models in COMADRE. For each of these, μ_1 was computed with formula (11) and τ was estimated by averaging several realizations of the random variable S/N described in the main-text (conditional on $N > 0$). One such realization can be obtained thanks to the following procedure, where $\mathbf{w} = (w_i)$ denotes the stable distribution:

```

parent ← False
while not parent do
  i ← random newborn stage chosen proportionally to the entries of  $(\sum_k f_{jk} w_k)_j$ 
  age, N, S ← 0, 0, 0
  alive ← True
  while alive do
    age ← age + 1
    offspring ← Poisson( $\sum_j f_{ji}$ )
    N ← N + offspring
    S ← S + offspring · age
    with probability  $1 - \sum_j s_{ji}$  do
      alive ← False
    else do
      i ← random stage chosen proportionally the entries of  $(s_{ji})_j$ 
  end while
  if N > 0 then
    parent ← True
end while
return S/N

```

Each estimate $\hat{\tau}$ is associated with a confidence interval $[\hat{\tau} - \varepsilon, \hat{\tau} + \varepsilon]$, where $\varepsilon = 2\hat{\sigma}/\sqrt{n}$ with $\hat{\sigma}$ the empirical standard deviation and \sqrt{n} the number of replicates. In order to get reliable estimates, the number of replicates n was doubled until $\varepsilon < 0.01\hat{\tau}$.

Because the probability of an individual producing some offspring during its lifetime can be arbitrarily small, this means that obtaining one realization of S/N with the procedure above can take an arbitrarily long time. To avoid getting stuck on a computation, all models for which $\hat{\tau}$ could not be computed with the desired precision in a reasonable time were ignored, and 1182 models were thus rejected. Because this is a non-negligible fraction of the 4564 models available, this has the potential to bias our results. However, note that since those models for which the probability of producing offspring during one’s lifetime is very small are precisely those for which we expect μ_1 to differ greatly from τ , if anything this will lead us to *underestimate* the difference between μ_1 and τ .

Finally, after performing these calculations, 11 models (0.28%) were discarded for having biologically unrealistic descriptors (e.g, $\lambda \approx 200$ or an average age of mothers in the stable population $\bar{A} \approx 10000$), leaving us with numerical values of μ_1 and τ for 2706 models of COMPADRE and 1165 models of COMADRE.

S7 Projection matrices for *A. mexicanum*

In this section, we detail a specific example of a real-world model in which μ_1 and τ differ greatly. These particular models were chosen because they have frequently been used as examples of matrix population models. For instance, one of them is shipped with the ULM software for studying population dynamics ([Legendre and Clobert, 1995](#)).

The following projection matrices for the tropical palm *Astrocaryum mexicanum* are from Appendix 6 of [Cochran and Ellner \(1992\)](#), who averaged them from several projection matrices of [Pinero et al. \(1984\)](#). Note that there is a small typo in the projection matrix for the *Low density* model given by [Cochran and Ellner \(1992\)](#): the entry (9, 8) of the projection matrix given is 0.8775, when it should be 0.08775. Correcting this, we find the same descriptors as in their Table 4.

The model is mostly size-based. Stage 1 corresponds to seedlings; stages 2–4 to non-reproducing juveniles and stages 5–10 to full-grown adults. In the matrices below, entries in bold correspond to reproductive transitions.

$$\mathbf{A}^{\text{high}} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \mathbf{1.4792} & \mathbf{8.1560} & \mathbf{9.9513} & \mathbf{14.259} & \mathbf{23.594} \\ 0.037349 & 0.83093 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.015881 & 0.89666 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.048969 & 0.95944 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.029778 & 0.90496 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.082074 & 0.91348 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.086520 & 0.90553 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.094467 & 0.87733 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.088200 & 0.88642 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.11358 & 0.9950 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{A}^{\text{med.}} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \mathbf{0.18385} & \mathbf{4.222} & \mathbf{8.41} & \mathbf{8.8405} & \mathbf{16.676} & \mathbf{19.904} \\ 0.03629 & 0.84127 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.014582 & 0.91636 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.058131 & 0.93735 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.051565 & 0.91462 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.065923 & 0.8468 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.1424 & 0.8725 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.1200 & 0.84332 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.14800 & 0.913030 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.086966 & 0.9950 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\mathbf{A}^{\text{low}} = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \mathbf{0.33} & \mathbf{0.918} & \mathbf{8.0875} & \mathbf{16.606} & \mathbf{13.068} & \mathbf{16.875} \\ 0.030332 & 0.850010 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0.026738 & 0.93928 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0.04966 & 0.94548 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.04804 & 0.9185 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.0815 & 0.9313 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.0687 & 0.86362 & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.13637 & 0.91225 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.08775 & 0.87867 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0.12133 & 0.9950 \end{pmatrix}$$

Table 1 lists some relevant descriptors of these models. The difference between μ_1 and τ is significant in all three scenarios – a factor 2 in the *Medium density* model. Finally, and most surprisingly, we see that in the *High density* case, μ_1 is greater than the expected lifespan conditional on reproduction. This counter-intuitive fact casts serious doubts on the relevance of μ_1 as a measure of reproductive timing in the life-cycle.

	High density	Medium density	Low density
μ_1	275.2	261.8	275.5
τ	152.0	131.3	184.8
T_{R_0}	197.6	169.2	153.6
\bar{A}	152.6	122.8	105.1
L	232.2	207.6	296.0

Table 1: Comparison of several measures of reproductive timing for three real-world models for the demography of the tropical palm *Astrocaryum mexicanum*, in part taken from Table 4 of [Cochran and Ellner \(1992\)](#): T_{R_0} denotes the R_0 generation time, which corresponds to the time it takes for the population to grow by a factor of its net reproductive rate; \bar{A} is the mean age of parents to offspring in a population that has reached its stable distribution; μ_1 is computed as in formula (11); τ and L are estimates of the mean age at reproduction and of the expected lifespan conditional on producing offspring, respectively. All values are expressed in years.

References

- Cochran, M. E., and S. P. Ellner. 1992. Simple methods for calculating age-based life history parameters for stage-structured populations. *Ecological Monographs* 62:345–364.
- COMADRE Animal Matrix Database. Data downloaded on 02/02/2019, version 2.0.1. Max Planck Institute for Demographic Research (Germany). Available at www.compadre-db.org.
- COMPADRE Plant Matrix Database. Data downloaded on 02/02/2019, version 4.0.1. Max Planck Institute for Demographic Research (Germany). Available at www.compadre-db.org.
- Daley, D. J., and D. Vere-Jones. 2003. *An Introduction to the Theory of Point Processes. Probability and its Applications*, 2nd ed. Springer-Verlag, New York (NY, USA).
- Kingman, J. F. C. 1992. *Poisson Processes*. Oxford Studies in Probability. Clarendon Press, Oxford (UK).
- Legendre, S., and J. Clobert. 1995. ULM, a software for conservation and evolutionary biologists. *Journal of Applied Statistics* 22:817–834. The ULM software can be downloaded at <http://www.biologie.ens.fr/~legendre/ulm/ulm.html>.
- Pinero, D., M. Martinez-Ramos, and J. Sarukhan. 1984. A population model of *astrocaryum mexicanum* and a sensitivity analysis of its finite rate of increase. *The Journal of Ecology* 72:977–991.